

SIMULATION OF BLOOD FLOW THROUGH A PATIENT-SPECIFIC CAROTID BIFURCATION RECONSTRUCTED USING DEEP LEARNING BASED SEGMENTATION OF ULTRASOUND IMAGES

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Abstract:

One of the diseases of the cardiovascular system is the formation of carotid artery stenosis. The existence of atherosclerotic plaque within the vessel wall causes changes in blood flow and can have serious consequences on the individual's health condition. Therefore, early and appropriate clinical diagnostics is very important. One of the first clinical examinations for this disease is the ultrasound (US) examination. Three-dimensional (3D) reconstruction and blood flow simulation could be used to overcome some of the drawbacks of the US examination and improve the overall diagnostics. An approach that combines the deep learning techniques and 3D reconstruction and meshing algorithms is applied within this study to create the model of patient-specific carotid bifurcation first and then to perform unsteady blood flow simulation, with realistic boundary conditions. This type of simulations can provide quantitative hemodynamic data to the clinicians during US examination and can further help to improve the diagnostics and ensure a treatment that is more adapted to the particular patient.

Key words: deep learning, image segmentation, 3D reconstruction, finite element method, unsteady blood flow.

Acknowledgement: The research presented in this study was part of the project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 755320-2 - TAXINOMISIS. This article reflects only the author's view. The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.